

IMPACT DAMAGE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF RESIN INFILTRATED TOUGHENED GRAPHITE/EPOXY PANEL

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ABSTRACT

The impact behavior and compression-after-impact (CAI) response of IM7-6K-5HS graphite fabric composites with three different toughened matrix materials at low velocity impact have been studied. The instrumented drop weight impact tests were performed at impact energy levels ranging from 13 joules to 29 joules with impact velocity of 2.4 m/sec to 3.6 m/sec. The CAI test was performed according to Boeing specification (BS7260) to determine the residual strength and modulus. The reduction in compressive strength and modulus was found to be 48% and 47% respectively. The extent of damage was investigated through ultrasonic C-scan and the failure modes after compression tests were studied using optical microscope (OM).

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the development of advanced high performance composite materials was mainly concerned with achieving high modulus and high strength materials. But the high strength materials have relatively low strains to failure (<1 percent) which makes them relatively brittle and contributes to their susceptibility to impact damage. Impact loading causes internal damage in the composite structures even at low velocity which can significantly reduce the residual strength, particularly in compression [1].

Although significant work has been performed [2-4] in the investigation of impact damage mechanisms of autoclave and compression molded composites, there is only limited information available on impact performance of composites made from new and emerging composites manufacturing techniques. The resin infiltration (RI) is one of those techniques which is gaining prominence in composites fabrication, as it offers a viable alternative for low-cost manufacturing. Due to the nature of this technique, resin flow through the fabric, resin viscosity, flow fronts, wettability and chemical composition are some of the many parameters that could influence the impact performance of the resulting laminate. One of the motivations for this work lies in investigation of different resin systems suitable for the RI technique using the same graphite fabric for their impact performance. The resin systems chosen here differ in respect of strength, modulus, chemical compatibility to the fiber, and resin viscosity.

Residual strength measurements are necessary to assess the damage tolerance of RI composite systems. Several studies [5-7] have reported the effect of impact damage on residual strength of the composite laminates. Strength reductions up to 40% have been observed in static and fatigue tests conducted on laminate coupons subjected to low velocity impact [8-9]. The

compression strength after impact test is widely employed as an indicator of residual strength [10] because the compression strength of the fiber reinforced composites is typically less than the tensile strength and hence become critical in the aircraft structural design. The specific mechanisms involved in compressive failure are not completely established, but are generally considered to involve both the matrix and the fiber failure. However, it is obvious that if considerable delamination takes place in the test specimen due to impact loading, the specimen could lose stability and fail by local buckling at the impacted areas [11]. Thus, for successful use of RI carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composites, an understanding of their impact behavior is important.

EXPERIMENTAL WORKS

MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN DESIGN

Quasi-isotropic laminates with [+45,0,-45,90,+45,0]_s stacking sequence were fabricated at Martin Marietta (MM) facilities through the RI technique. Woven graphite fabric of five harness satin (5HS) architecture (Hercules IM7-6K) was used with three different toughened matrix materials denoted as: L10 [AroCy L10-CoAcAc], Tactix [Tactix 123-H41] and Epon [Shell Epon 862-W]. For future discussions in this article the material systems will be referred to by their matrix names, i.e. L10, Tactix and Epon. The fiber volume fraction was calculated by both the theoretical and digestion methods (ASTM D3171 and ASTM D2734). The average fiber volume fraction was found to be 55%-58%. The specimens were cut from the panel with a diamond saw and the side edges were polished to fine finish. The final specimen dimensions were 15.24 cm x 10.16 cm x 0.445-0.422 cm (6 inch x 4 inch x 0.175-0.166 inch).

IMPACT TESTS

The drop weight impact tests were performed with an impactor of 5.44 kg (12 lbs) weight, with a hemispherical steel tip of 1.59 cm (5/8 inch) diameter. The tower was instrumented for the measurement of impact velocity within 0.5 cm/sec at a point no more than 0.254 cm away from the point of impact. A steel base plate of 2.54 cm (1 inch) thickness with 7.62 cm by 12.7 cm (3 inch by 5 inch) through cutout was used to hold the specimen during impact. Hard rubber tip guiding pins were used to hold the specimen centrally over the cut-out. The specimens were subjected to impact loads, ranging from 13 joules to 29 joules (10 ft-lbs to 20 ft-lbs.) impact energy with impact velocity of 2.4 m/sec to 3.6 m/sec (8 ft/sec to 12 ft-lbs). The specimen and the impact support fixture is shown in Fig. 1.

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) TESTS

CAI tests were performed to assess the residual compressive strength after impact. These tests were conducted in a 22 kips MTS hydraulic testing machine using the test fixture according to the Boeing Specification, BS7260, as shown in Fig. 2. The undamaged specimens were tested in a 50 kips MTS machine at Martin Marietta. The specimen was aligned by adjusting the side plates (adjustable guides), making sure that the specimen was held perpendicular to the base plate of the test fixture. The side plates were fastened properly to ensure lateral support for the specimen, and the top plate was placed at the top of the specimen. The tests were performed under stroke control at a cross head speed of 0.127 cm/min. (0.05 in/min.). The load vs. displacement plots were recorded during CAI test on a x-y plotter.

ULTRASONIC C-SCAN

Ultrasonic C-scan tests were performed under an immersion type pulse-echo mode utilizing a 2.25 MHz focused transducer to assess the through-the-thickness condition of the specimen. Reflections from the front and back surfaces of the specimen were captured on the ultrasonic equipment monitor, and gated. All the specimens were subjected to ultrasonic C-scan testing before and after impact tests. The specimens were also scanned after the compression tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

CONTACT FORCE VS. TIME

Comparison of Contact Force vs. Time (F-t) history for the L10, Tactix and Epon material systems at 13 joules and 29 joules impact level are shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) respectively. All material systems show almost similar F-t history with respect to peak load, fracture initiation time (i.e., time required to reach the peak load) and propagation time at 13 joules impact level. It may be seen that the F-t history is almost symmetrical about the peak at this impact level. In contrast, the specimens subjected to 29 joules impact level indicate a non-symmetrical F-t history. The F-t history shows a short duration (<0.001 sec) preinitial fracture region, followed by an initial fracture region (near the peak load) and a distinctly long-duration post initial fracture region (0.001-0.004 sec). The multiple load drops in the post initial fracture region of Fig. 3(b) indicate the initiation and failure progression in the samples.

ENERGY VS. TIME

Comparison of Energy vs. Time (E-t) history for three material systems at 13 joules and 29 joules are shown in Fig. 4(a) and 4(b) respectively. At 13 joules impact level, the energy absorbed by the three material systems are found to be almost similar in magnitude; 5.5 joules, 6.03 joules and 5.85 joules for the L10, Tactix and Epon systems respectively. However, at 29 joules impact level, the energy absorbed by the L10 systems was higher by 2 joules as compared with the Tactix and Epon systems (For the L10 system the energy absorbed was \cong 29 joules, while for the Tactix and Epon systems, it was \cong 27 joules). It is observed in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) that there is a distinct difference in the pattern of the E-t curves at two impact levels. At the lower impact level (13 joule) the E-t curves in all systems plateaus at 13 joule and then levels off smoothly at approximately 5.5 joules. However, at higher impact level (29 joule), the E-t curves continue to rise similar to the initial E-t history of Fig 4(a), and then level off at the peak value. The difference in this E-t behavior at two impact levels indicate the difference in the response of the material systems with respect to the velocity of the impact.

COMPRESSION AND CAI TESTS

Table 1 shows the test matrix adopted for the compression tests. Compression strength, modulus and strain-to-failure are obtained from the load vs. displacement curves as shown in Fig. 5. Weibull analysis was employed to obtain statistical information such as characteristics strength (CS), characteristics modulus (CM) and shape factor (SF) from the experimental data [12]. The shape factor indicates the degree of consistency in the compression test data.

Table 1 Test Matrix for Compression Tests

Weibull Parameter	Virgin (unimpacted)			13 joules Level			29 joules Level		
	L10 ⁴	Epon ³	Tactix ³	L10 ⁴	Epon ²	Tactix ²	L10 ⁴	Epon ³	Tactix ²
CS (MPa)	246.4	322.7	279.8	218.5	211.3	178.4	170.7	167.65	145.6
SF	10.61	12.76	23.31	29.28	8.89	15.23	27.53	31.8	80.23
CM (GPa)	24.12	28.30	22.41	22.53	14.91	14.25	14.24	15.61	13.90
SF	17.26	60.83	-	7.6	10.35	8.46	14.8	54.34	18.0
Strain-to-failure (%)	1.22	1.41	1.26	1.15	1.29	1.43	1.45	1.30	1.14
SF	8.9	8.6	-	12.4	9.4	6.8	8.9	11.46	103

Superscript indicate the number of specimen tested under each condition.

Response of Virgin Specimens

From Fig. 5 the Epon and Tactix systems are seen to exhibit higher compression strength and strain-to-failure as compared to the L10 systems. The compression behavior of the laminates is closely related to two factors that govern the resulting fiber/matrix interface: a) chemical composition of the matrix system and, b) flow characteristics (i.e., viscosity) of the matrix system. Investigation of the matrix specifications shows that the Epon and Tactix systems are epoxy based matrices, while the L10 is a liquid dicyanate monomer. It is well known that epoxy has good adhesion to the sizings of the graphite fiber [13], while very limited information is available about the compatibility of the L10 matrix to graphite fibers. Furthermore, from the materials specification data sheet (MSDS) the viscosities of the neat resins ranked as; L10: 1.2 poise, Epon: 20-23 poise and Tactix: 44-56 poise. From these considerations, there is sufficient evidence to suggest that the fiber-matrix bonding of the Epon and the Tactix systems is stronger than the L10 system. The low viscosity characteristics of the L10 matrix in conjunction with the RI manufacturing process influences the wettability and the resulting fiber/matrix bonding. It is believed that this difference in the matrix property contributed to the variation in this compression strength and moduli of the three material systems.

Response of Impacted Specimens

The variation of residual compression strength and modulus vs. impact energy for all material systems are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 respectively. The explanation ensues:

(i) At 13 joules Impact Level (Low Energy Level)

The L10 system shows the lowest strength and strain-to-failure at the virgin state. However, at 13 joules impact energy level, the L10 system is seen to exhibit better residual strength and modulus as compared to the Epon and Tactix systems. The reduction in strength and modulus for the L10 system is found to be only 11% and 6% respectively. In contrast, the reduction of the strength for both the Epon and the Tactix systems are found to be $\cong 35\%$, and the reduction of modulus is found to be 36% for the Epon system and 47% for the Tactix system.

These observations may be explained from the resin and interface characteristics: The residual compression properties are influenced by neat resin properties. Ultimate strength for the neat matrices are; L10: 158 MPa, Epon: 128 MPa and Tactix: 110 MPa. For the Tactix and Epon systems, the low impact energy level causes invisible matrix damage accumulation in the vicinity of the impact. For the L10 system due to its higher neat resin strength, this system shows improved residual properties; the strength and modulus of this system are found to be higher. Figures. 8(a) and 8(b) attempt to analyze the results from the interface point-of-view. The Epon and Tactix systems at their virgin state exhibit strong fiber/matrix bonding as explained in the previous section. After subjecting these systems to impact, due to the strong fiber/matrix bonding, the energy is distributed conically in the vicinity of the impact, but is not effectively dissipated in the laminate. The energy level is not sufficient to debond/open the interfaces. However, it is sufficient to cause localized weakening of the material in the vicinity of the strike. The failure of these laminates occur at the impact locations (localized failure) after the CAI tests. The localized nature of failure can also be seen from the ultrasonic C-scan of the failed Tactix specimen as shown in figure 9(d). Due to the weak nature of the fiber/matrix interface in the L10 system, the energy of impact appears to get dissipated effectively from the impact location. Here also, energy is not sufficient to debond the interface, however the weakening of the materials is not as localized as the Tactix or Epon systems. The modulus and strength of the L10 system thereby exhibit improvement over the counterpart systems after the CAI tests.

(ii) At 29 joule Impact Level (High Energy Level)

At 29 joules impact energy level, the residual strengths and moduli of the three systems are within 14% and 10% of each other respectively. The reduction in strength is found to be $\cong 12\%$ for both the Epon and the Tactix systems and is found to be 20% for the L10 system as compared to 13 joules impact. The residual properties at this energy level appears to be fiber dominated because all the matrices are prone to loss in stiffness and cracking. The influence of viscosity or chemical composition of the matrix is less prevalent.

NON DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE

After machining, all the specimens were subjected to ultrasonic C-scan prior to any testing. The samples were scanned again after the impact tests as well as after compression tests. Typical ultrasonic C-scans for (a) the virgin state, (b) after the 13 joules impact, (c) after the 29 joules impact and (d) after the CAI tests are shown in Figs. 9. The extent of impact damage indicated by the black near the center of the C-scan was measured by superposing the C-scan on a graph paper and estimating the area of damage occupied by the grids (squares). This measured area is denoted as "damage area" and plotted against the impact energy in Fig. 10. For all impact levels, the Epon material system exhibited the lowest "damage area" followed by the Tactix and the L10 systems. This is in agreement with the schematic shown in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). The rate of increase of "damage area" is more at low impact energy level (0-13 joules) as compared to high energy level (13-29 joules) for Tactix and Epon, except for the L10 system which exhibits a linear trend from 0 to 29 joules.

The measured "damage area" is plotted against the residual compression strength and the residual compression modulus in Figs. 11 and 12 respectively. The damage tolerance of the L10 systems is seen to be highest, while the Epon system exhibited the least damage tolerance. The Tactix system showed damage tolerance intermediate to these systems. The damage tolerance is thereby seen to be influenced by various factors such as matrix compositions, viscosity characteristics and fiber/matrix interface etc. The strong interface in the Epon and Tactix systems adversely affects the damage tolerance as it causes severe localized reduction in stiffness. In contrast, an intermediate interface for the L10 system shows improvement in the damage tolerance.

Optical microscopy further validates the C-scan results. From Figs. 13(a), 13(b) and 13(c) it is seen that Tactix and Epon systems exhibited localized damage development due to formation of kink bands, fracture of tensile side fiber and localized matrix cracking. The L10 system shows distributed failure and energy dissipation through fracture paths that occur from multiple cracks to form delamination of several layers in addition to the above mechanisms.

CONCLUSIONS

Following conclusions are drawn from the present investigation

1. At low energy level (13 joules) the impact response of the three material systems is similar in terms of the F-t distribution. The 13 joules impact level is not sufficient to create delamination/disbonds in any systems. However, CAI tests indicated that the mechanisms of the failure after impact were different in the Tactix and Epon systems vs. L10 system. Failure zone was highly localized after CAI tests for Tactix and Epon systems, while it was more distributed for the L10 system. As a consequence, the L10 system exhibits higher toughness, higher damage tolerance and progressive failure as compared to Tactix and Epon systems.
2. At high impact energy level (29 joules), it was apparent that all the systems underwent tensile side fiber fracture and visible indentation at the location of the impact. The CAI response showed residual moduli and strength value within 10% to 14% of each other respectively. This trend indicated that the interface conditions at the impact damage zone govern the final failure in all the systems. Failure is through kink band formation, shearing of fibers and delamination.
3. The utility of the L10 system under impact loading is justified at the compromise of slight reduction in its compressive properties when compared with Tactix and Epon systems. This behavior of L10 is a combined result of various factors beginning with the RI process, chemical composition, morphology of the resin systems and the resulting composite fiber/matrix interface.

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Figure 1 : (a) Impact Specimen (b) Impact Support Fixture

Figure 2. Boeing Compression Fixture

Figure 3. Comparison of Contact Force vs. Time Plot (a) 13 joules (b) at 29 joules

Figure 4. Comparison of Energy vs. Time Plot (a) 13 joules (b) at 29 joules

Figure 5. Load vs. Displacement Plot at Virgin State (Unimpacted)

Figure 6. Comparison of Residual Compression Strength vs. Impact Energy Plot

Figure 7. Comparison of Residual Compression Modulus vs. Impact Energy Plot

Figure 8. Schematic Diagram of Energy Dissipation (a) Tactix and Epon Systems (b) L10 System

Figure 9. Ultrasonic C-scans (a) the virgin state (b) after 13 joules Impact (c) after 29 joules Impact (d) after the CAI Test

Figure 10. Comparison of Impact Damage Area vs. Impact Energy Plot

Figure 11. Comparison of Residual Compression Strength vs. Damage Area Plot

Figure 12. Comparison of Residual Compression Modulus vs. Damage Area Plot

Figure 13. Optical Micrographs (Edge View) after CAI Test at 29 joule Impact Level